

ELECTROLYSIS OF MANGANOUS SULPHATE AND SULPHURIC ACID.

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Results are given of a detailed investigation on the electrolysis of manganous sulphate in the presence of sulphuric acid. Optimum conditions have been worked out for the anodic oxidation of manganous sulphate. The role of the various electrochemical factors, such as the relative proportions of manganous sulphate and sulphuric acid, the temperature, the inter-electrode distance, the current density at the anode and at the cathode, the current concentration, the duration of electrolysis, the anode material, the superposition of A.C. on D.C., agitation of the bath by steam, and of some eighteen catalysts, has been investigated. Ferric sulphate, potassium iodate, cobaltous sulphate, lead acetate, hydrofluoric acid improved considerably the current efficiency for the anodic oxidation. The probable role of these catalysts is discussed. A mechanism of the anodic oxidation of manganous sulphate in sulphuric acid is indicated.

Oxidation of manganous salts to permanganic acid, both chemically and electrolytically, seems to have been the subject of much extensive investigation (*cf.* Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry," Longmans Green and Co., London, 1932, Vol. XII, Part I, pp. 293, 431). The technical method for the regeneration of chromic acid in the electrolysis of chromium sulphate and sulphuric acid (*cf.* Askenasy and Revai, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1913, 19, 344) suggests the possibility of a similar method for permanganic acid. Electrolysis of manganous sulphate in the presence of sulphuric acid yields different oxidation products of manganese depending mainly upon the concentration of manganous sulphate, the temperature, and the concentration of the acid employed. Much uncertainty, however, exists, in the literature regarding the precise nature of the oxidation products obtained electrolytically (*cf.* Meyer, *ibid.*, 1916, 22, 201). A detailed study has, therefore, been made of the electrolysis of manganous sulphate and sulphuric acid under varied conditions (*vide infra*) with a view to defining a set of conditions for the optimal yields of oxidation products.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In all the experiments reported, manganous sulphate used was prepared from the cheap Indian material pyrolusite by its reduction with carbon and subsequent treatment with sulphuric acid under the *optimum* conditions, worked out by H. K. Joshi in these laboratories. The electrolysis was carried out in a cylindrical glass vessel of about 300 c.c. capacity, kept immersed in a water thermostat and maintained at the desired temperature. The electrodes used were of smooth platinum except in experiments reported in Table IX, showing the *influence of anode material*. The electrodes were disposed *horizontally*; the anode was kept at the bottom of the bath and cathode just in flush with the upper surface. Experience had shown the marked convenience of this arrangement in facilitating free escape of hydrogen and thus minimising the cathodic reduction. The circuit included a precision ammeter, electrolytic cell and suitable resistances in series and a voltmeter connected across the terminals of the electrolytic cell. The current used for the electrolysis was taken from a 220 D.C. main and was regulated by resistance bulbs and rheostats. To ascertain the optimum conditions for the oxidation, the influence of the following factors was studied over ranges as indicated below:—

	Optimum conditions.		
(i) Conc. of H_2SO_4 (30-90%)	...	...	60%
(ii) Conc. of $MnSO_4$ (1.5-9%)	—	—	7.5%

(vii) Temperature (75° - 80°)	...	...	60°
(viii) Inter-electrode distance (2.9 cm.)	...	...	5.5 cm
(ix) Anodic C.D. (100-480 amp /dm ²)	...	...	300 amp/dm ² .
(x) Cathodic C.D. (52-750 amp /dm ²)	...	...	270 amp /dm ² .
(xi) Current conc. (0.0105-0.025)	...	...	0.019 amp /c.c.

Under the optimum conditions, a study was also made of the influence of the duration of electrolysis, nature of the anode material, superposition of A.C. on D.C., of passing steam through the electrolyte during electrolysis and of the addition of a number of catalysts.

Method of Estimation of the Oxidation Products and Calculation of Current Efficiency.—A definite volume (5 c.c.) of the electrolysed solution (160 c.c.) was taken and to it was added a known excess (10 c.c.) of standard solution of (N/10) oxalic acid. The solution was then heated to about 70° and the excess of oxalic acid was back-titrated against standardised solution of N/100-KMnO₄. From this, the active oxygen content in 5 c.c. and therefore, in the total volume (160 c.c.) was computed.

The current efficiency in any experiment was calculated on the basis that 1 faraday (i.e., 26.86 amp-hours of electricity) yields 8 g. of active oxygen.

TABLE I.

Influence of sulphuric acid conc.

Electrolyte = 160 c.c. MnSO₄ = 7.5 g. in 100 c.c. soln. Current = 3 amp. Anodic C.D. = 300 amp./dm². Cathodic C.D. = 270 amp./dm². Duration = 20 min. Temp. = 60° . Inter-electrode distance = 5.5 cm. P.D. = 6 volts.

5 C.c. of the electrolysed solution taken for estimation.

Sulphuric acid in 100 c.c. soln.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
30 g.	12.2 c.c.	0.031 g.	10.5%
45	59	0.151	51.0
60	80	0.205	69.0
75	35	0.089	30.0
90		Manganous sulphate precipitates	

TABLE III.

Effect of temperature.

Conc. of H₂SO₄ = 60 g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Temp.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
15°	58 c.c.	0.148 g.	50.0%
30	64	0.163	55.2
50	69.6	0.178	60.0
60	80	0.205	69.0
70	64.9	0.166	56.0
80	60.3	0.154	52.0

TABLE II.

Influence of manganous sulphate conc.

Conc. of H₂SO₄ = 60 g. in 100 c.c. soln.
(Other conditions same as in Table I.)

MnSO ₄ in 100 c.c. soln.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
1.5 g.	13 c.c.	0.033g.	11.2%
3.0	32.7	0.084	28.2
4.5	45.2	0.116	39.0
6.0	63.5	0.163	54.8
7.5	80	0.205	69.0
9.0	81	0.207	69.9

TABLE IV.

Variation of inter-electrode distance.

Conc. of H₂SO₄ = 60 g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Inter-electrode distance.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
2 cm.	69.6 c.c.	0.178 g.	60.0%
4	76.5	0.197	66.0
5.5	80	0.205	69.0
8	80	0.205	69.0
9	80	0.205	69.0

TABLE V.

Effect of current density.

Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 60$ g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Current.	Time.	Anodic C.D. amp./dm. ²	Cathodic C.D. amp./dm. ²	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N-KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
1 amp.	60 min.	100	91	77	0.197 g.	66.4%
2	30	200	180	77.9	0.199	67.2
3	20	300	270	79.9	0.205	68.9
4	15	400	360	73	0.187	63.0
4.5	13½	450	4.5	60.3	0.154	52.0
4.8	12½	480	4.3	59.1	0.151	51.0

TABLE VII.

Effect of current concentration.

Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 60$ g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Vol. of electrolyte.	Current conc. amp./c.c.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N-KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in the soln.	Current efficiency.
120 c.c.	0.025	67.1 c.c.	0.171 g.	57.9%
160	0.019	20	0.205	69.0
200	0.015	71.3	0.183	61.5

TABLE IX.

Variation of anode material.

Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 60$ g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Anode material.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N-KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
Smooth platinum	79.9 c.c.	0.205 g	68.9%
Platinised platinum	58.6	0.149	50.5
Lead	87	0.223	75.0
Graphite	No oxidation of $MnSO_4$; Disintegration of the electrode.		

TABLE VI.

Variation of cathodic current density.

Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 60$ g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Dimensions of the electrode.	Cathodic C.D. amp./dm. ²	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N-KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
2.4 × 2.4 cm ²	52	56 c.c.	0.143 g.	48.3%
1.5 × 1.3	154	75	0.193	64.7
1.1 × 1	270	80	0.205	69.0
0.8 × 0.5	750	77.9	0.199	67.0

TABLE VIII.

Effect of the duration of electrolysis.

Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 60$ g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Time.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N- KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
5 min.	32 c.c.	0.074 g.	100%
10	49	0.125	84.5
20	80	0.205	69.0
60	208.1	0.535	69.0
90	Manganese dioxide precipitates.		

TABLE X.

Influence of superposition of A.C. on D.C.

Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 60$ g. in 100 c.c. soln.
Other conditions same as in Table I.

Conditions of the experiment*	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.01N-KMnO ₄)	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
Without superposi- tion of A.C. on D.C.	80 c.c.	0.205 g.	69.0%
*With A.C. superpos- ed on D.C.	90.4	0.232	78.6

TABLE XI.

*Effect of passing steam during the electrolysis.*Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 65.55$ g. in 100 c.c. soln. Other conditions same as in Table I.

Conditions of the experiment.	Final volume of the soln	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.02N-KMnO ₄).	Total active oxygen in the soln.	Current efficiency.
Without passing steam	160 c.c.	80 c.c.	0.05 g.	69.0%
With passing steam	178	52	0.149	50.0

TABLE XII.

*Effect of addition agents.*Conc. of $H_2SO_4 = 60$ g. in 100 c.c. soln. Amount of the addition agent = 1 g. (or c.c.) in 100 c.c. soln. (Other conditions same as in Table I.)

Addition agent.	P.D. in volta.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.02N-KMnO ₄).	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.	Addition agent.	P.D. in volta.	Active oxygen in 5 c.c. soln. (0.02N-KMnO ₄).	Total active oxygen in 160 c.c. soln.	Current efficiency.
K ₂ CrO ₄	7	92.7 c.c.	0.237 g.	80.0%	Ti(SO ₄) ₃	7	80.6 c.c.	0.206 g.	69.5%
KClO ₃	7.8	93.2	0.238	80.5	V ₂ O ₅ (NO ₃) ₃	7.8	83	0.212	71.7
Ag ₂ SO ₄	6.7	83	0.212	71.6	NaWO ₄	7.8	82.3	0.212	71.0
CoSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	7	95.5	0.244	82.4	HF	7.8	84.6	0.217	73.0
H ₃ PO ₄	6.7	79.2	0.203	69.3	Na ₂ HPO ₄	7	82.3	0.211	71.0
K ₂ S ₂ O ₈	7	76.9	0.197	66.4	KF	7.8	83.5	0.214	72.0
KI	7	73.1	0.189	63.9	HCl	7.5	60.5	0.155	53.2
Ti ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	7	71.9	0.177	62.0	KIO ₃	7.8	77	0.248	83.6
Ce(SO ₄) ₃	6.5	98	0.251	84.5	Pb(CH ₃ COO) ₂ · 3H ₂ O	7.8	85	0.228	73.3

Results showing the influence on current efficiency of varying proportions of sulphuric acid and of manganous sulphate in the mixture, and of temperature are shown graphically in Fig. 1. Fig. 2 shows similarly the influence of the duration of electrolysis and of anodic and cathodic current density on the current efficiency.

DISCUSSION.

The foregoing results indicate that the anodic oxidation of manganous sulphate in presence of sulphuric acid is dependent upon a large number of parameters such as the electrolyte concentration, the current density at the anode and cathode, the temperature, the electrode material, etc. This is conveniently expressed in respect of the current efficiency which is 100% under ideal conditions. Any discrepancy in this might be ascribed to the possible disturbing factors: (i) chemical or electrochemical decomposition of the resulting product or products, (ii) occurrence of side reactions such as oxygen evolution at the anode, *i.e.*, other than the main one for which current efficiency is calculated, or (iii) solvational effects leading partly to the formation of molecular or ionic complexes in the conducting mixtures.

When 60% sulphuric acid containing 7.5% manganous sulphate are electrolysed between the two platinum electrodes, pink colour develops at the anode instantaneously, *i.e.*, the moment

the current is switched on (*cf.* our results). The colour deepens to dark or brown-red and deep violet on prolongation of the electrolysis due to the formation of manganic sulphate, manganese disulphate and probably traces of permanganic acid. Much uncertainty exists in the literature regarding the precise nature of the oxidation products obtained electrolytically. The considerations of the earlier workers show that the products of the anodic oxidation of manganous sulphate and sulphuric acid vary under differing conditions. A very low concentration of manganous sulphate and low temperatures are favourable for the formation of permanganic acid (*cf.* Sem, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1915, 21, 426; Ruscon, *Arch. Farm. Spec. Sci. aff.*, 1919, 27, 94; Campbell, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 22, 66); with higher concentrations of manganous sulphate and sulphuric acid manganic sulphate and manganic disulphate are probably formed (*cf.* Elbs, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1900, 7, 260; Goerbig, "Beitrage zur Kenntnis der Sulphate und Nitrate des 3-bzw. 4-wertigen Mangans," Halle a.S., 1911). Meyer (*loc. cit.*) criticises several of the statements of Sem. He points out that manganic salts exist in solutions of various colours including violet, brown-red, dark green and olive-green and not only in the first two as stated by Sem. He further adds that the whole of the variously coloured solutions have practically identical absorption spectra. Consequently, he says, that Sem is not justified in subdividing manganic salts into two classes from the difference of colour. The oxidation of manganous sulphate, under the operative conditions, to manganic sulphate and manganic disulphate might possibly be represented as

in concentrated solutions.

The presence of sulphuric acid plays a very important role in the anodic oxidation of manganous sulphate as is seen from the results (*cf.* Table I) of the wide variation of sulphuric acid concentration. The electrolysis of 30% sulphuric acid leads to the precipitation of manganese dioxide after a short duration, probably due to the hydrolytic decomposition of the resulting products especially in dilute acid. Very low current efficiency (10.5%) under the stated condition might probably be ascribed to the discharge of OH ion at the anode and their subsequent recombination to form water and oxygen. The current efficiency progressively increases with the concentration of sulphuric acid up to a particular limit (60%) and then diminishes (*cf.* curve 1, Fig. 1). This might probably be attributed to increased stability of the products, especially in the stronger solutions of the acid employed. A marked diminution in the current efficiency at high concentration of the acid (above 60%) appears to be chiefly due to the precipitation of manganous sulphate and its subsequent reducing action on the oxidation products formed.

As discussed previously, the concentration of manganous sulphate, the depolarizer, exerts a marked influence on the nature of the oxidation products obtained electrolytically. At very low concentration permanganic acid is formed, but in stronger solutions, manganic sulphate, manganic disulphate and other oxidation products of manganese are the chief products. In the present investigation the concentration of manganous sulphate is varied in the range 1.5–9%, the products obtained being mainly manganic sulphate and manganic disulphate and probably traces of permanganic acid. An examination of the results in Table II reveals that the yield and consequently the current efficiency of the oxidation products increase steadily (*cf.* curve 2, Fig. 1) with the concentration of manganous sulphate, the depolariser, up to a particular limit (7.5%), after which it remains almost constant with further increase in concentration. This is in agreement with the general findings in oxidation reactions. Higher concentrations (above 9%) of manganous sulphate could not be employed owing to the complications arising out of its

precipitation in strongly acid media. It should also be noted that once the precipitation of manganous sulphate occurs, the yield of oxidation products falls considerably.

Results recorded in Table III show that temperature variation (15° - 80°) has a marked influence on the current efficiency. The influence of an increase of temperature on an electrolytic oxidation, when oxygen is simultaneously being evolved, can vary. It acts favourably by increasing the velocity of diffusion of the depolariser. But it also lowers the oxygen over-voltage and thus facilitates the discharge of oxygen. According as one or the other of these two effects predominates it will be better to work at a low or a high temperature (*cf.* Allmand and Ellingham, "Principles of Applied Electro-chemistry," London, 1931, p. 104). Furthermore, the stability of the products formed needs also be considered. Thus, the rise in current efficiency (*cf.* curve 3 in Fig. 1) with the rise in temperature up to 60° (*cf.* our results) might be ascribed to increased diffusion of the depolariser and its subsequent oxidation at the anode. The diminution in yields, especially at higher temperature (above 60°), might be due to much of the current being utilised in discharging oxygen at the anode, being facilitated by lowering of its over-voltage. The reducing action of manganous sulphate on the oxidation products and the unstable nature of the latter, especially at higher temperatures, might also account for the lowering of the yields.

In any electrolytic reaction the oxidation product formed at the anode may diffuse towards the cathode and be subsequently reduced. It is to be anticipated that with the increase of inter-electrode distance up to a particular limit, the current efficiency may increase due to a diminution in reduction. Results reported in Table IV are in agreement with this deduction.

The variation of current density materially affects the anodic process. Results shown in Table V indicate that the current efficiency increases very gradually with the increase of anodic C.D. (*cf.* curve 2, Fig. 2) up to a particular limit (300 amp./dm²), probably due to an increase in oxygen over-voltage and a corresponding diminution in its evolution. Increased rate of diffusion of the depolariser and its subsequent oxidation at the anode might also partly explain increased yields at high C.D. With further increase of C.D. (above 300 amp./dm²) the current efficiency, however, diminishes, due presumably to increased oxygen evolution at the anode.

Results recorded in Table VI show that the current efficiency is low at low cathodic C.D. (52 amp./dm².) probably due to the fact that the oxidation products formed at the anode might be reduced appreciably by the nascent hydrogen evolved at the cathode.

The variation of current concentration affects the current efficiency of oxidation appreciably. This is illustrated from our data shown in Table VII.

As in all oxidation reactions the duration of electrolysis exerts a profound influence on the course of the anodic reaction. The oxidation of manganous sulphate in the presence of sulphuric acid is rapid and immediate as is noticed by the instantaneous formation of pink colour at the anode. The current efficiency is 100% for shorter durations (5 mins.) of electrolysis (*cf.* results in Table VIII). It shows a rapid but gradual diminution with the progress of electrolysis (*cf.* curve 1 in Fig. 2). After 1½ hours of electrolysis an immediate precipitation of manganese dioxide takes place due to increased concentration of the oxidation products and their hydrolytic decomposition.

The nature of the anode material is very important in oxidation reactions as is seen from the results recorded in Table IX. With graphite anode there was no oxidation of manganous sulphate. It appears that the whole of the current is utilised in discharging oxygen at the anode. The carbon particles produced by the disintegration of the graphite anode foul the solution. Results with smooth and platinised Pt show that better yields are obtained with the former probably due to high oxygen over-voltage. High current efficiency (75%) with Pb anode appears to be due to the catalytic influence of PbO₂ formed at the anode. Catalytic influence of the anode material, especially PbO₂, seems to have been noticed earlier. For example Regelsberger (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1899, 6, 388) found that chromium salts, which are not oxidised at Pt anodes, are readily oxidised on the addition of a small amount of lead salts which form a PbO₂ layer on the anode (*cf.* also Muller and Solier, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1905, 11, 863).

The chemical effects of pure alternating currents are in any case inconsiderable and not particularly remarkable. When, however, an alternating current is superposed on a direct current, some striking results are obtained (*cf.* Table X). The current efficiency improves markedly. This might probably be due to a considerable diminution in oxygen over-voltage and a corresponding lowering in the oxidising potential. The magnitude of the decrease produced in the degree of irreversibility of the direct current electrode process, depends on

(a) the ratio $\frac{\text{alternating current strength}}{\text{direct current strength}}$; (b) the frequency of the alternating current (*cf.* Allmand

and Ellingham, *op. cit.* p. 147). Ghosh (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 733), Stepanow (*Chem. Abst.*, 1916, 10, 2431), Archibald and Wartenberg (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1911, 17, 812) and others have also shown that the voltage required for a particular electrolysis at a given current density will be lowered by the use of a superposed alternating current.

An examination of the results shown in Table XI reveals that the current efficiency of oxidation falls considerably (50%) by passing steam through the electrolyte. This might be accounted for as follows: The passage of steam during the electrolysis might cause a considerable agitation of the electrolyte which might produce a lowering in the oxygen over-voltage thus facilitating increased oxygen evolution at the anode. The agitation might also bring about marked decomposition of the oxidised products.

Not only the material of the electrode but also additions to the electrolyte can act as catalysts in anodic oxidations. Some of these 'oxygen-carriers' are very important. Addition of quite a large number of substances has been tried and their influence studied (*cf.* results in Table XII). Ce(SO₄)₂, KIO₃, CoSO₄, 7H₂O, KClO₃, K₂CrO₄, Pb(CH₃COO)₂, 3H₂O, HF, KF, Ag₂SO₄, etc.,

were found to be the best in descending order. The rest were found to be less promising; while agents like $Tl_2(SO_4)_2$, KI and HCl were found to be detrimental or negative catalysts. Addition of 1 c.c. of conc. HCl to 100 c.c. of the solution, for example, lowers the current efficiency from 69% to 52.2%. This appears to be due to the oxidation of the addendum by the powerful oxidising products formed. The addition of 1 g. of $Ce(SO_4)_3$ in 100 c.c. solution raises the efficiency to a considerable extent (84.5%). This might be due to the fact that the catalyst being a powerful oxidising agent oxidises the depolariser; it gets subsequently reoxidised at the anode and is used up again in oxidising the depolarizer, the result of the whole cyclic operation being the increased oxidation of manganous sulphate. High efficiency (82.4%) of oxidation with the addition of $CoSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ can be explained in a somewhat similar manner. Cobaltous sulphate may be oxidised to cobaltic sulphate ($Co^{++} \rightarrow Co^{+++}$) which may subsequently react with the depolariser regenerating cobaltous sulphate. Increased efficiency with the addition of $KClO_3$, K_2CrO_4 and of KIO_3 might possibly be attributed to their high oxidising property. Favourable effects of $Pb(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ might be ascribed to the catalytic influence of PbO_2 film formed at the anode, as discussed previously. Addition of 1 c.c. of HF in 100 c.c. solution raises the current efficiency from 69% to 73%, probably due to a considerable rise in the anode potential. The results with the addition of KF can be explained on similar lines. The mode of action of the catalysts is clear and simple in some cases but sometimes this is not so. The work of earlier investigators leads to similar conclusions.

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